

females reared on IR36 rice plants (163 eggs/female). We will be studying LF growth, development, longevity, and reproduction on this artificial diet for several generations. □

Effect of insecticides on rice gall midge (GM) and its parasite *Platyaster* sp.

G. Logiswaran, C. Durairaj, and P.C. Sundara Babu, Agricultural Entomology Department, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai 625104, India

We studied the effect of three granular and three liquid insecticides on GM and the occurrence of its parasite *Platyaster* sp. during 1986 wet season. Treatments were applied 35 d after transplanting. GM incidence (% affected tillers) was estimated 20 d after treatment (DAT). Parasite occurrence was estimated 30 DAT by calculating percentage of puparia parasitized.

GM incidence was significantly lowest with carbofuran 3 G treatment, which was on par with chlorpyrifos 40 EC,

Effect of insecticides on GM and its parasite *Platyaster* sp. Madurai, India, 1986 wet season.

Treatment	Formulation ^a (%)	Dose (kg ai/ha)	GM incidence (%) 20 DAT ^b	Parasitization (%) 30 DAT ^c
Chlorpyrifos	10 G	1.0	8.4 (2.87)	90.0 (75.0)
Cartap	4 G	1.5	5.8 (2.38)	60.0 (50.8)
Carbofuran	3 G	1.0	3.8 (1.95)	60.0 (50.8)
Chlorpyrifos	40 EC	0.5	4.4 (2.07)	53.0 (46.9)
Monocrotophos	36 WSC	0.25	5.4 (2.26)	76.0 (61.2)
Phosalone	35 EC	0.5	9.9 (3.12)	80.0 (63.4)
Control	-	-	14.5 (3.77)	86.0 (68.8)
CD (P = 0.05)			(0.6)	(6.7)

^aG = granule, EC = emulsifiable concentrate, WSC = water-soluble concentrate. ^bFigures in parentheses are *x* values. ^cFigures in parentheses are arc sine values.

monocrotophos 36 WSC, and cartap 4 G (see table). Percentage of parasitization was lowest with chlorpyrifos 40 EC, which was on par with carbofuran 3 G and cartap 4 G. The insecticides effective on GM were toxic to the parasite. The highest

percentage of parasitization was recorded with chlorpyrifos 10 G, indicating that it is safe for the parasite; the EC of the same insecticide recorded the lowest percentage of parasitization, indicating that it is highly toxic to the parasite. □

Toxicity of five insecticides to the cricket *Metioche vittaticollis* (Stal) (Orthoptera: Gryllidae), a predator of some insect pests of rice

E.G. Rubia and B.M. Shepard, Entomology Department, IRRI

The use of selective insecticides is important to protect the natural enemies of insect pests of rice. We studied the toxicity of some commonly used insecticides to *M. vittaticollis*, a predatory cricket in ricefields.

Test compounds from different groups of chemicals were used: BPMC, buprofezin, carbosulfan, monocrotophos, and cypermethrin. Insecticides were applied topically using a microapplicator. Mortality was recorded 24 h after treatment.

Based on LD₅₀ (μg/g), the order of decreasing toxicity of the 5 insecticides to *M. vittaticollis* was cypermethrin > carbosulfan > monocrotophos >

Toxicity^a of 5 insecticides to *M. vittaticollis*. IRRI insectary, 1985.

Insecticide ^b	LD ₅₀ (after 24 h)	
	μg/g	μg/insect
BPMC	4.51 (3.433-5.833)	0.05416 (0.0412-0.0700)
Monocrotophos	0.4008 (0.316-0.500)	0.00481 (0.00380-0.00601)
Cypermethrin	0.1442 (0.109-0.184)	0.00173 (0.00131-0.00221)
Carbosulfan	0.2308 (0.164-0.300)	0.00277 (0.00197-0.00361)
Buprofezin	>41,667	>500

^aFiducial limits in parentheses. ^bCalculated as ED₅₀ (the dosage that will give 50% mortality and abnormalities of the test animals).

BPMC > buprofezin (see table). The growth inhibitor buprofezin was not toxic and did not affect the molting of *M. vittaticollis* nymphs.

These results suggest that using selective chemicals such as buprofezin will conserve important biological control agents such as *M. vittaticollis*. □

The International Rice Research Newsletter and the IRRI Reporter are mailed free to qualified individuals and institutions engaged in rice production and training. For further information write: IRRI, Communication and Publications Dept., Division R, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.